

CLINICAL FEATURES OF HYMENOLEPIASIS IN CHILDREN

**Matyakubova Oysha Urinovna,
Abdullayeva Dilfuza Kadamovna,
Artiqov Ikrom Axmedjonovich,
Ibodullayeva Sevvara Salibayevna**

Urgench branch Tashkent medical academy, Khorezm, Uzbekistan

Abstract: The widespread prevalence of infectious and parasitic diseases among humans and animals is facilitated by the intensive contamination of various environmental objects — such as soil, water, household items, vegetables, greens, fish, and meat products—with helminth eggs. Failure to observe personal hygiene rules and the lack of basic preventive measures, not only among people but also among animals, contribute to environmental contamination with parasite eggs and larvae. All of this leads to an increase in cases of parasitic infections not only among animals but also among people, particularly among children.

Keywords: Hymenolepiasis, infestation, children, environment, food, water.

КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ГИМЕНОЛЕПИДОЗА У ДЕТЕЙ

Аннотация. Широкому распространению инфекционных и паразитарных заболеваний среди людей и животных способствует интенсивная контаминация различных объектов окружающей среды: почвы, воды, предметов быта, овощей, зелени, рыбных и мясных продуктов их возбудителями — яйцами гельминтов. Несоблюдение правил личной гигиены, отсутствие элементарных мер профилактики не только среди людей, но и среди животных, приводящее к загрязнению объектов окружающей среды яйцами и личинками паразитов, - все это приводит к росту случаев паразитарных заболеваний не только среди животных, но и среди людей, в том числе и среди большинства детей.

Ключевые слова: гименолепидоз, инвазия, дети, окружающая среда, продукты питания, вода.

Hymenolepis nana, known as the dwarf tapeworm, is one of the most widespread tapeworms that causes hymenolepiasis. These parasites consume vital nutrients, microelements, and vitamins necessary for human life, negatively impacting children's health. They release toxins that weaken the immune system. Hymenolepiasis is widespread across the globe, with humans serving as the primary source of infection. The disease affects people of all ages and genders, depending on specific and communal environmental conditions.

This contagious parasite is found in many countries and is the most common cause of cestodiasis in both tropical and temperate climate zones. Infection rates are particularly high among children. Although *Hymenolepis diminuta* can also cause hymenolepiasis, it is much less common. *Hymenolepis nana* is unique among cestodes in completing its full life cycle in a single host, without

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needing an intermediate host. This parasite can complete its life cycle entirely within a human (auto-infection), a process that occurs in the intestines.

Infection usually occurs through ingesting eggs found in the feces of an infected person, often via contaminated food. Insects can sometimes act as carrier hosts. Morphological characteristics of parasite eggs in feces are crucial for diagnosis. The eggs accumulate in the stomach or small intestine, and the larvae (oncospheres) penetrate the microvilli of the upper intestine, attaching to the intestinal walls. The larvae develop into cysticercoids and return to the intestinal lumen to mature. Adult worms reach maturity within a few weeks and can grow up to 40 mm in length.

Hymenolepiasis may be asymptomatic even with a high parasite load. Some patients may experience headaches, dizziness, loss of appetite, abdominal pain, diarrhea, and irritability. Blood tests in some cases show eosinophilia. Severe infections can be caused by internal auto-infection, where the eggs mature and complete their life cycle within the intestines. This characteristic can lead to complications.

Among children with hymenolepiasis, the most commonly affected age groups are preschoolers and school-aged children (45% and 34%, respectively), while 20% are younger children. This suggests that the infection is more prevalent in children during periods of active interaction with the environment.

Common symptoms in children with hymenolepiasis include: constant fatigue and irritability (100%), headaches (92%), persistent facial rashes (78%), hair and nail loss (76%), decreased appetite (70%), and anemia (72%). Gastrointestinal symptoms such as persistent abdominal pain (77.8%), constipation, and diarrhea (55.5%) were also observed. Nervous system symptoms were present in 64.4% of children, including mood swings, irritability, fatigue, and weakness. Many children experienced disturbed sleep and bruxism (teeth grinding). In 35% of cases, children exhibited severe symptoms like dizziness, eye blinking, nose twitching, and shoulder jerking (tics). Additionally, 80% had poor concentration, 62.2% had weight loss, and 82.2% were diagnosed with anemia. In 42.2% of cases, physical developmental delays, memory problems, and learning difficulties were observed. Allergic reactions were found in 63.4% of children. Older children experienced more severe complications such as chronic pyelonephritis (in 45% of affected children), sinusitis (22%), and weakened immune systems. 38% had intestinal dysbiosis or prolonged diarrhea.

Diagnosis of helminth infections typically involves microscopic examination of stool samples. If hymenolepiasis is suspected in a child, fresh stool should be collected in a special container and sent to the lab on the same day. Detecting parasite eggs of *Hymenolepis nana* or *Hymenolepis diminuta* in feces is necessary for confirmation. Treatment includes praziquantel or niclosamide. Because cysticercoids are less sensitive during development, effective treatment may require higher doses or longer treatment durations.

Preventive measures are crucial in controlling hymenolepiasis: regular handwashing after using the toilet, coming indoors, and before meals is essential. Stool analysis is typically performed to differentiate gastrointestinal and parasitic infections. If a parasitic infection has been diagnosed before, the test can also be used to monitor the effectiveness of anthelmintic therapy.

In conclusion, children with hymenolepiasis exhibit a variety of clinical symptoms, including general toxic effects, gastrointestinal and neurological issues, and allergic reactions. The disease can be difficult to detect, especially in early stages, making early diagnosis and treatment crucial. Stool analysis should be repeated 14 days after treatment, then monthly for six months. If parasite eggs are still detected, another course of treatment is necessary.

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